

AIFA News about Clinical Trials in Italy for Covid-19

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AIFA is providing information about the clinical trials for Covid-19 at the following link <https://www.aifa.gov.it/sperimentazioni-cliniche-covid-19> , last update made on 14 May 2020.

Here in the following some information given to update a discussion I made in "Drugs used in Italy against Covid-19", Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234> The aim is that of include drugs not previously mentioned.

DEF-IVID19 - IRCCS OSPEDALE SAN RAFFAELE – MILANO - Uso di Defibrotide in infusione intravenosa per ridurre la progressione dell'insufficienza respiratoria in pazienti con polmonite severa da COVID-19 - 08/05/2020

"**Defibrotide**, sold under the brandname Defitelio, is a mixture of single-stranded oligonucleotides that is purified from the intestinal mucosa of pigs. It is used to treat veno-occlusive disease of the liver of people having had a bone marrow transplant, with different limitations in the US and Europe. It works by protecting the cells lining blood vessels and preventing blood clotting; the way it does this is not well understood. There is a strong risk of bleeding in the brain, eyes, lungs, gastrointestinal tract, urinary tract, and nose. Some people have hypersensitivity reactions. It was approved in Europe in 2013 and in the US in 2016". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Defibrotide>

COMBAT-19 - IRCCS OSPEDALE SAN RAFFAELE – MILANO - A randomized, double blind, placebo-Controlled trial of Mavrilimumab for Acute respiratory failure due To COVID-19 pneumonia with hyper-inflammation: the COMBAT-19 trial - 07/05/2020

"**Mavrilimumab** is a human monoclonal antibody that inhibits human granulocyte macrophage colony-stimulating factor receptor (GM-CSF-R). Mavrilimumab was discovered as CAM-3001 by Cambridge Antibody Technology and is being developed by MedImmune, Inc. as an investigational drug for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. ... As of 2013, two further clinical studies were reported to be underway in rheumatoid arthritis patients to investigate these effects further. In early 2017 the phase IIb study was reported to be showing promising results". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mavrilimumab>

PRECOV - IRCCS OSPEDALE SAN RAFFAELE – MILANO - Studio controllato, in singolo cieco, sugli effetti della idrossiclorochina nella prevenzione di COVID-19 in operatori sanitari a rischio - 07/05/2020

"**Hydroxychloroquine** (Plaquenil) is considered a disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drug (DMARD). It can decrease the pain and swelling of arthritis. It may prevent joint damage and reduce the risk of long-term disability. Hydroxychloroquine is in a class of medications that was first used to prevent and treat malaria". <https://www.rheumatology.org/I-Am-A/Patient-Caregiver/Treatments/Hydroxychloroquine-Plaquenil>

ARCO - INMI "L. SPALLANZANI" - ROMA - Adaptive Randomized trial for therapy of Corona virus disease 2019 at home with oral antivirals (ARCO-Home study) (Darunavir-cobicistat (DRV-c), Lopinavir-ritonavir (LPV-r), Favipiravir (FAV) e Idrossiclorochina (HCQ)) - 07/05/2020

Darunavir-cobicistat "È un inibitore delle proteasi boosterato con cobicistat. Cobicistat ne migliora il profilo farmacocinetico e inibendo il citocromo P450 isoenzima 3A4 rallenta il metabolismo di darunavir ed incrementa la sua esposizione farmacologica. L'associazione ha dimostrato la sua efficacia nell'ambito della ART per il trattamento dell'HIV".

https://www.aifa.gov.it/documents/20142/0/darunavir_cobicistat_01.04.2020.pdf/34c4938d-5b25-e39c-abb3-b42e3c874e1b

"**Lopinavir/ritonavir** è una associazione farmacologica, caratterizzato dalla unione in una unica capsula di 133,3 mg di lopinavir e 33,3 mg di ritonavir. L'associazione è utilizzata per il trattamento dell'infezione da HIV e combina lopinavir (che non è in commercio come farmaco a sé stante) con una dose subterapeutica di ritonavir. Nella associazione il ruolo svolto da ritonavir è quello di potenziatore farmacocinetico ed inibitore del citocromo P450 isoenzima 3A4 con conseguente inibizione del metabolismo di lopinavir ed incremento della sua esposizione farmacologica".

<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lopinavir/ritonavir>

"Il **Favipiravir**, noto anche come T-705 (commercializzato come Avigan o Favilavir), è un farmaco antivirale che possiede un'attività diretta contro molti virus a RNA. È stato sviluppato dalla Toyama Kagaku Kōgyō, una consociata giapponese della Fujifilm Holdings Corporation. Chimicamente è un 6-fluoro-3-idrossi-2-pirazinecarbrossammide. Come alcuni farmaci antivirali sperimentali (T-1105 e T-1106), è un derivato della pirazinecarbrossammide".

<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Favipiravir>

CAN-COVID - NOVARTIS RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT - Studio di fase 3°, multicentrico, randomizzato, in doppio-cieco, controllato verso placebo per valutare l'efficacia e la sicurezza di canakinumab sulla sindrome di rilascio delle citochine in pazienti con polmonite indotta da COVID-19 (CAN-COVID) - 06/05/2020

"Il **Canakinumab** (nome commerciale Ilaris) è un anticorpo monoclonale di tipo umano sviluppato dalla Novartis, che è stato studiato per il trattamento di patologie quali artrite reumatoide, artrite idiopatica giovanile sistemica, BPCO, diabete tipo 1 e 2, e alcune malattie oculari. L'uso è approvato dall'EMA e dalla FDA nelle "sindromi periodiche associate alla criopirina" ... Gravi forme di sindrome familiare autoinfiammatoria da freddo (FCAS) ... Il farmaco è un anticorpo monoclonale specifico anti IL1 β (Interleuchina-1beta) ed agisce bloccandone l'attività biologica. Uno studio pubblicato su *Reumatology* dell'aprile 2011 indica un'efficacia superiore al triamcinolone acetone nel trattamento di forme acute di gotta. Il Canakinumab è il primo farmaco ad essere approvato, nel settembre 2011, in Giappone per il trattamento delle sindromi periodiche associate alla criopirina (CAPS). Nelle 2017 è stato pubblicato uno studio in cui il Canakinumab è stato impiegato per ridurre il rischio di un secondo evento cardiovascolare, ... Si è inoltre inaspettatamente dimostrato in grado di diminuire la mortalità per tumore, diminuendo del 75% la probabilità di morte per tumore al polmone e dimezzando la mortalità per tutti gli altri tipi di tumore. Tuttavia ha leggermente incrementato il rischio di morte per infezione".

<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Canakinumab>

"**Canakinumab** (INN, trade name Ilaris, previously ACZ885) is a human monoclonal antibody targeted at **interleukin-1 beta**. Canakinumab was approved for the treatment of cryopyrin-associated periodic syndromes (CAPS) by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in June 2009 and by the European Medicines Agency in October 2009. CAPS is a spectrum of several

autoinflammatory syndromes. ... Canakinumab was being developed by Novartis for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, but this trial was completed in October 2009. Canakinumab is also in phase I clinical trials as a possible treatment for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, gout, and coronary artery disease." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Canakinumab>

FIBROCOV - UCSC - ROMA

Studio di fase 2/3 in aperto, randomizzato, a due gruppi paralleli multicentrico per valutare l'efficacia e la sicurezza della somministrazione endovenosa di pamrevlumab, in confronto alla gestione clinica standard, in pazienti con infezione da SARS-CoV-2 (FivroCov) - 05/05/2020

"**Pamrevlumab** (INN; development code FG-3019) is a humanized monoclonal antibody designed for the treatment of idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis and pancreatic cancer. This drug was developed by FibroGen, Inc.". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pamrevlumab>

HS216C17 - ASST FATEBENEFRAPELLI SACCO - A Multi-center, Randomized, Double-blind, Placebo-controlled, Phase III Clinical Study Evaluating the Efficacy and Safety of Favipiravir in the Treatment of Adult Inpatients with COVID-19-General Type (HS216C17). 05/05/2020

AZI-RCT-COVID-19 - UNIVERSITÀ DEL PIEMONTE ORIENTALE (UPO) - Studio clinico randomizzato controllato open label per valutare l'efficacia e la sicurezza dell'associazione di idrossiclorochina più azitromicina versus idrossiclorochina in pazienti affetti da polmonite da COVID-19 (AZI-RCT-COVID19) - 04/05/2020

"L'idrossiclorochina (Plaquenil® cp da 200 mg o corrispondente generico) è un analogo della cloroquina chimicamente molto simile e che ne condivide il meccanismo d'azione. È un antimalarico, attualmente utilizzato nel nostro Paese in campo reumatologico alla dose di 200 mg x 2 anche per periodi molto prolungati; esiste quindi ampia esperienza clinica (superiore rispetto alla cloroquina) riguardo alla sua tollerabilità".

https://www.aifa.gov.it/documents/20142/1123276/idrossiclorochina_29.04.2020.pdf/386d6ea3-c79b-6437-f457-23d33df74256

"Azitromicina (compresse da 500mg o polvere per sospensione orale alla concentrazione di 200 mg/5ml) è un antibiotico della famiglia dei macrolidi, autorizzato per il trattamento di infezioni delle alte e basse vie respiratorie, infezioni odontostomatologiche, infezioni della cute e dei tessuti molli, uretriti non gonococciche, ulcere molli. Il dosaggio indicato è 500 mg al giorno per 3 giorni consecutivi".

https://www.aifa.gov.it/documents/20142/1123276/azitromicina_05.05.2020.pdf/272d910e-1f59-d69c-28f0-805f096ae4d3

Read please carefully the updates in both documents, about the use of hydroxychloroquine and Azithromycin for Covid-19.

About the association of Hydroxychloroquine and Azithromycin, we discussed in <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3830359>

AMMURAVID - SOCIETÀ ITALIANA DI MALATTIE INFETTIVE E TROPICALI (SIMIT)

Cumulative adaptive, multiarm, multistage and multicentre randomized clinical trial with immunotherapy for Moderate COVID-19 (the AMMURAVID trial) - 01/05/2020

AMMURAVID uses ocilizumab, Sarilumab, Siltuximab, Canakinumab, Baricitinib, Metilprednisolone (see <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>).

"**Tocilizumab**, also known as **atlizumab**, is an immunosuppressive drug, mainly for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis It is a humanized monoclonal antibody against the interleukin-6 receptor (IL-6R). **Interleukin 6 (IL-6)** is a cytokine that plays an important role in immune response and is

implicated in the pathogenesis of many diseases, such as autoimmune diseases, multiple myeloma and prostate cancer". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tocilizumab>
"Tocilizumab" <https://www.drugs.com/monograph/tocilizumab.html>
"Atlizumab: anti-IL-6 receptor antibody-Chugai, anti-interleukin-6 receptor antibody-Chugai, MRA-Chugai". BioDrugs. 2003;17(5):369-72. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/14498766>
"Actemra/RoActemra (tocilizumab)" Roche <https://www.roche.com/products/product-details.htm?productId=42bf9d08-8573-491a-944a-fdbc030ec44b>
"Tocilizumab" by Adith Venkiteshwaran. MAbs. 2009 Sep-Oct; 1(5): 432–438. doi: 10.4161/mabs.1.5.9497. PMID: 20065633

"**Sarilumab** (trade name Kevzara) is a human monoclonal antibody against the **interleukin-6** receptor. ... US FDA approval on 22 May 2017 and European Medicines Agency approval on 23 June 2017." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sarilumab>.
"Sarilumab enters clinical trial for COVID-19, spotlighting 'key role' for IL-6". March 19, 2020. <http://archive.is/PFlDw> "Sarilumab (Kevzara) — jointly developed Regeneron and Sanofi — is a fully human, monoclonal antibody that inhibits the interleukin-6 (IL-6) pathway by binding and blocking the IL-6 receptor. According to the pharmaceutical companies' joint statement, IL-6 may play a role in driving the overactive inflammatory response in the lungs of patients who are severely or critically ill with COVID-19."

"**Siltuximab** (INN, trade name Sylvant; also known as CNTO 328, **anti-IL-6** chimeric monoclonal antibody or **cCLB8**) is a chimeric (made from human and mouse proteins) monoclonal antibody. It **binds to interleukin-6**. Siltuximab has been investigated for the treatment of neoplastic diseases." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Siltuximab>
"Il Siltuximab è un anticorpo monoclonale che agisce sull'**IL-6**, è studiato come antitumorale. E' commercializzato come Sylvant; noto anche come CNTO 328. E' studiato per il trattamento di tumori metastatici come il carcinoma a cellule renali, tumore alla prostata, e per la malattia di Castleman, tra altri tipi di tumore." <https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Siltuximab>
"Sylvant è un medicinale contenente il principio attivo siltuximab." <https://www.my-personaltrainer.it/farmaci/sylvant.html>

"**Baricitinib**, sold under the brand name Olumiant among others, is a drug for the treatment of **rheumatoid arthritis** (RA) in adults whose disease was not well controlled using RA medications called tumor necrosis factor (TNF) antagonists. It acts as an inhibitor of janus kinase (JAK), blocking the subtypes JAK1 and JAK2." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Baricitinib>

"**Methylprednisolone**, sold under the brand name Depo-Medrol among others, is a corticosteroid medication used **to suppress the immune system and decrease inflammation**. Conditions in which it is used include .. ". Serious side effects are reported, and common side effects with long term use. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Methylprednisolone>

XPORT-COV-1001 - KARYOPHARM THERAPEUTICS INC - A Phase 2 Randomized Single-Blind Study to Evaluate the Activity and Safety of Low Dose Oral Selinexor (KPT-330) in Patients with Severe COVID-19 Infection (XPORT-CoV-1001) - 28/04/2020

"**Selinexor** (INN, trade name Xpovio; development code KPT-330) is a selective inhibitor of nuclear export used as an anti-cancer drug. It works by binding to exportin 1 and thus blocking the transport of several proteins involved in cancer-cell growth from the cell nucleus to the cytoplasm, which ultimately arrests the cell cycle and leads to apoptosis. It is the first drug with this mechanism of action. Selinexor was granted accelerated approval by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in July 2019, for use in combination with the corticosteroid dexamethasone for the treatment

of adult patients with relapsed refractory multiple myeloma (RRMM) who have received at least four prior therapies and whose disease is resistant to several other forms of treatment, including at least two proteasome inhibitors, at least two immunomodulatory agents, and an anti-CD38 monoclonal antibody. In clinical trials, it was associated with a high incidence of severe side effects, including low platelet counts and low blood sodium levels. As of May 2020, it is in clinical trials for treatment of COVID-19 at locations including hospitals like Lehigh Valley Hospital". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Selinexor>

ESCAPE - INMI "L. SPALLANZANI" - ROMA - Studio clinico di fase 3, randomizzato, in aperto, multicentrico volto a confrontare l'efficacia clinica e la sicurezza di Sarilumab per via endovenosa in aggiunta allo standard of care rispetto allo standard of care, nel trattamento di pazienti con polmonite severa da COVID-19. (ESCAPE) 28/04/2020 - On the use of Sarilumab, see <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

PROTECT - IST. SCIENTIFICO ROMAGNOLO PER LO STUDIO E LA CURA DEI TUMORI - IRST IRCCS - MELDOLA - PROTECT: A randomized study with Hydroxychloroquine versus observational support for prevention or early phase treatment of Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) - IRST 100.47 - 27/04/2020

REPAVID-19 - DOMPÉ FARMACEUTICI SPA - OSPEDALE SAN RAFFAELE - Adaptive phase 2/3, randomized, controlled multicenter study on the efficacy and safety of Reparixin in the treatment of hospitalized patients with COVID-19 pneumonia (REPAVID-19) -24/04/2020

"**Reparixin** is an orally available inhibitor of CXC chemokine receptor types 1 (CXCR1) and 2 (CXCR2), with potential antineoplastic activity. Upon administration, reparixin allosterically binds to CXCR1 and prevents CXCR1 activation by its ligand interleukin 8 (IL-8 or CXCL8). This may cause cancer stem cell (CSC) apoptosis and may inhibit tumor cell progression and metastasis. ... In addition, reparixin inhibits CXCR2 activation and may reduce both neutrophil recruitment and vascular permeability during inflammation or injury". <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Reparixin>

COVID-SARI - ASST FATEBENEFRAPELLI SACCO - Pilot study on the use of sarilumab in patients with covid-19 infection (COVID-SARI) – Studio sull'utilizzo di sarilumab - 24/04/2020

X-COVID - ASST GRANDE OSPEDALE METROPOLITANO NIGUARDA - Enoxaparina per la tromboprofilassi di pazienti ospedalizzati COVID-19 positivi: comparazione fra dosaggio di 40 mg in monosomministrazione versus 40 mg bigiornalieri. Un trial clinico randomizzato X-COVID - 22/04/2020

"L'**enoxaparina** (chiamata anche in fase di sperimentazione PK 10169), utilizzata come sale di sodio, è un frammento di eparina a basso peso molecolare. È preparata per depolimerizzazione dell'estere benzilico dell'eparina estratta dalla mucosa porcina. L'enoaparina presenta, rispetto all'eparina naturale, un netto aumento del rapporto tra l'attività anti-Xa e quella anti-IIa, rapporto che diventa superiore a 4. Pertanto nell'animale essa svolge buona attività antitrombotica con minima interferenza sul sanguinamento, essendo inoltre trombolitica. Nell'uomo è possibile confermare una buona attività antitrombotica senza significativa interferenza con i test della coagulazione". <https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enoxaparina>

BARCIVID - AZIENDA OSPEDALIERA UNIVERSITARIA PISANA - MultiCentre, randomised, Phase IIa clinical trial evaluating efficacy and tolerability of Baricitinib as add-on treatment of patients with COVID-19 compared to standard therapy - 22/04/2020

INHIXACOVID - UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA - Intermediate dose enoxaparin in hospitalized patients with moderate-severe COVID19: a pilot phase II single-arm study, 22/04/2020

COLCOVID - AZIENDA OSPEDALIERO-UNIVERSITARIA DI PARMA - Colchicina per contrastare la risposta infiammatoria in corso di polmonite da COVID 19 - 20/04/2020 See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

"**Colchicine** is a medication used to treat gout and Behçet's disease. In gout, it is less preferred to NSAIDs or steroids. Other uses include the prevention of pericarditis and familial Mediterranean fever. Common side effects include gastrointestinal upset, particularly at high doses. Severe side effects may include low blood cells and rhabdomyolysis. Colchicine works by decreasing inflammation via multiple mechanisms. " <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Colchicine>

"Colchicine, in the form of the autumn crocus, has been used as early as 1500 BC to treat joint swelling." <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Colchicine>

"Colchicum autumnale, commonly known as autumn crocus, meadow saffron or naked ladies, is a toxic autumn-blooming flowering plant that resembles the true crocuses, but is a member of the plant family Colchicaceae, unlike the true crocuses which belong to the family Iridaceae. Despite the vernacular name of "meadow saffron", this plant is not the source of saffron, which is obtained from the saffron crocus, *Crocus sativus* - and that plant too is sometimes called "autumn crocus"." https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Colchicum_autumnale

COLVID-19 - AZIENDA OSPEDALIERA DI PERUGIA - Trattamento con COLchicina di pazienti affetti da COVID-19: uno studio pilota (COLVID-19) - 11/04/2020 See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

SOLIDARITY - OMS/UNIVERSITÀ DI VERONA - An international randomised trial of additional treatments for COVID-19 in hospitalised patients who are all receiving the local standard of care 09/04/2020

HYDRO-STOP - ASUR - AV5 ASCOLI PICENO - Hydroxychloroquine sulfate early administration in symptomatic out of hospital COVID-19 positive patients (Hydro-Stop-COVID19 Trial) - 08/04/2020

TOCILIZUMAB 2020-001154-22 - F. HOFFMANN - LA ROCHE LTD - A randomized, double-blind, placebocontrolled, multicenter study to evaluate the safety and efficacy of tocilizumab in patients with severe covid-19 pneumonia (Tocilizumab 2020-001154-22) - 30/03/2020 See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

COP-COV - UNIVERSITÀ DI OXFORD (UK) - Chloroquine/ hydroxychloroquine prevention of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) in the healthcare setting; a randomised, placebo-controlled prophylaxis study (COPCOV) - 30/03/2020

RCT-TCZ-COVID-19 - AUSL - IRCCS DI REGGIO EMILIA - Uno studio randomizzato multicentrico in aperto per valutare l'efficacia della somministrazione precoce del Tocilizumab (TCZ) in pazienti affetti da polmonite da COVID-19 - 27/03/2020 See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

SARILUMAB COVID-19 - SANOFI-AVENTIS RECHERCHE & DÉVELOPPEMENT - An adaptive phase 2/3, randomized, double-blind, placebocontrolled study assessing efficacy and safety of sarilumab for hospitalized patients with COVID-19 (Sarilumab COVID-19). 26/03/2020

SOBI.IMMUNO-101 - SOBI - A phase 2/3, randomized, open-label, parallel group, 3-arm, multicenter study investigating the efficacy and safety of intravenous administrations of emapalumab, an anti-interferon gamma (anti-IFN γ) monoclonal antibody, and anakinra, an interleukin-1(IL-1) receptor antagonist, versus standard of care, in reducing hyper-inflammation and respiratory distress in patients with SARSCoV-2 infection (Sobi.IMMUNO-101) - 25/03/2020

"**Emapalumab**, marketed under the trade name Gamifant, is an anti-interferon-gamma (IFN γ) antibody used for the treatment of hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH), which currently has no cure. Adverse effects - In the clinical trials that lead to emapalumab's FDA approval, the most commonly reported adverse effects were infections (56%), high blood pressure (41%), infusion reactions (27%), and fever (24%). Serious adverse effects occurred in about half of the subjects studied in the clinical trial that led to its FDA approval". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emapalumab>

"**Anakinra** (brand name Kineret) is a biopharmaceutical drug used to treat rheumatoid arthritis. It is a recombinant and slightly modified version of the human interleukin 1 receptor antagonist protein. It is marketed by Swedish Orphan Biovitrum. ... More than ten percent of people taking Anakinra have injection site reactions, headaches, and have increased levels of cholesterol in their blood. Between one and ten percent of people have severe infections, decreased white blood cells, or decreased platelets. It is unclear if taking Anakinra increases the risk of getting cancer; studies are complicated by the fact that people with rheumatoid arthritis are already at higher risk of getting cancer". <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Anakinra>

TOCIVID-19 - ISTITUTO NAZIONALE TUMORI, IRCCS, FONDAZIONE G. PASCALE – NAPOLI - StudioMulticenter study on the efficacy and tolerability of tocilizumab in the treatment of patients with COVID-19 pneumonia (TOCIVID-19) - 18/03/2020 See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

GS-US-540-5773 - GILEAD SCIENCES, INC- A Phase 3 Randomized Study to Evaluate the Safety and Antiviral Activity of Remdesivir (GS-5734™) in Participants with Severe COVID-19. (GS-US-540-5773 Study) - 11/03/2020 - See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>

GS-US-540-5774 - GILEAD SCIENCES, INC - A Phase 3 Randomized Study to Evaluate the Safety and Antiviral Activity of Remdesivir (GS-5734™) in Participants with Moderate COVID-19 Compared to Standard of Care Treatment. (GS-US-540-5774 Study) - 11/03/2020 - See <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3818234>